

Circle packing in arbitrary domains: supplemental material

Paolo Amore

Facultad de Ciencias, CUICBAS, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`paolo@ucol.mx`

Damian de la Cruz

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`ddelacruz1@ucol.mx`

Valeria Hernandez

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`vhernandez20@ucol.mx`

Ian Rincon

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`irincon@ucol.mx`

Ulises Zarate

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
`uzarate@ucol.mx`

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Abstract

We report some of the configurations of congruent disks in a number of different domains, obtained with the algorithm of ref. [1]. The domains that we have considered are rectangles, crosses, ellipses, as well as a series of domains corresponding to a continuous deformation of the circle to the cardioid and multiply connected domains (circles and ellipse with a hole). Many of these configurations had not been studied before.

1 Introduction

This document contains the supplemental material of our paper, [1]. It is meant to provide an illustration of the algorithm that we have devised, and it allows to deal with arbitrary domains. All the cases that we have studied are in two dimensions, but the algorithm can also be used in three or more dimensions. A reader interested in the details of the algorithm should refer to [1].

Section 2 contains the explicit diagrams of many configurations whereas section 3 contains the corresponding Voronoi diagrams.

2 Explicit diagrams

2.1 Rectangle

2.1.1 $N = 14$

Figure 1: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 14$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 2: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 14$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.1.2 $N = 25$

Figure 3: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 25$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 25$
 $a = 6.36$
 $\rho = 0.7704761$

$N = 25$
 $a = 6.97$
 $\rho = 0.8091358$

Figure 4: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 25$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.1.3 $N = 36$

Figure 5: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 6: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.1.4 $N = 49$

Figure 7: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 8: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.1.5 $N = 60$

Figure 9: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 60$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 60$
 $a = 1.97$
 $\rho = 0.841989$

$N = 60$
 $a = 2.34$
 $\rho = 0.8055368$

$N = 60$
 $a = 2.8$
 $\rho = 0.8444694$

Figure 10: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 60$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 60$
 $a = 3.75$
 $\rho = 0.7853982$

$N = 60$
 $a = 4.31$
 $\rho = 0.8447175$

$N = 60$
 $a = 6.67$
 $\rho = 0.7850059$

$N = 60$
 $a = 7.5$
 $\rho = 0.841079$

Figure 11: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 60$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.1.6 $N = 64$

Figure 12: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 64$
 $a = 2.13$
 $\rho = 0.8288442$

$N = 64$
 $a = 2.75$
 $\rho = 0.8164976$

$N = 64$
 $a = 3.01$
 $\rho = 0.8381652$

Figure 13: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 64$
 $a = 3.62$
 $\rho = 0.7886544$

$N = 64$
 $a = 3.82$
 $\rho = 0.7853929$

$N = 64$
 $a = 4.0$
 $\rho = 0.7881715$

Figure 14: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 64$
 $a = 4.01$
 $\rho = 0.7881497$

$N = 64$
 $a = 4.59$
 $\rho = 0.8462123$

$N = 64$
 $a = 8.03$
 $\rho = 0.8387534$

Figure 15: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 64$
 $a = 16.0$
 $\rho = 0.785398$

$N = 64$
 $a = 17.42$
 $\rho = 0.8287227$

Figure 16: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.1.7 $N = 120$

Figure 17: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 120$
 $a = 1.76$
 $\rho = 0.8491482$

$N = 120$
 $a = 2.2$
 $\rho = 0.8599127$

$N = 120$
 $a = 2.87$
 $\rho = 0.8537832$

Figure 18: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 19: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 20: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

2.2 Cross

2.2.1 $N = 36$

Figure 21: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside cross.

Figure 22: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside cross.

$N = 36$
 $a = 2.33$
 $\rho = 0.7842113$

$N = 36$
 $a = 8.71$
 $\rho = 0.7889016$

Figure 23: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside cross.

2.2.2 $N = 49$

Figure 24: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside cross.

$N = 49$
 $a = 1.11$
 $\rho = 0.7809542$

$N = 49$
 $a = 1.36$
 $\rho = 0.8013664$

Figure 25: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside cross.

$N = 49$
 $a = 2.85$
 $\rho = 0.7742513$

$N = 49$
 $a = 3.2$
 $\rho = 0.8010358$

Figure 26: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside cross.

2.2.3 $N = 64$

Figure 27: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside cross.

Figure 28: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside cross.

$N = 64$
 $a = 3.8$
 $\rho = 0.7757019$

$N = 64$
 $a = 4.21$
 $\rho = 0.8079943$

Figure 29: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside cross.

2.3 Ellipse

2.3.1 $N = 37$

Figure 30: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 37$ equal circles inside ellipse.

2.3.2 $N = 61$

Figure 31: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 61$ equal circles inside ellipse.

2.3.3 $N = 91$

Figure 32: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside ellipse.

Figure 33: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside ellipse.

2.4 Continuous deformation of a circle into a cardioid

For this case we use the following parametrization which has constant area of π :

$$C(u) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{2+a^2}} \cdot (\cos u - a \sin^2 u, (1 + a \cos u) \sin u)$$

2.4.1 $N = 37$

Figure 34: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 37$ equal circles inside circle deforming into a cardioid.

$N = 37$
 $a = 0.75$
 $\rho = 0.7857632$

$N = 37$
 $a = 0.79$
 $\rho = 0.7857584$

Figure 35: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 37$ equal circles inside circle deforming into a cardioid.

2.4.2 $N = 61$

Figure 36: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 61$ equal circles inside circle deforming into a cardioid.

Figure 37: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 61$ equal circles inside circle deforming into a cardioid.

2.4.3 $N = 91$

Figure 38: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside circle deforming into a cardioid.

Figure 39: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside circle deforming into a cardioid.

2.5 Cardioid

Figure 40: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 41: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 42: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 43: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 44: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 45: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 46: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 47: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 48: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 49: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 50: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

2.6 Annulus with hole

Figure 51: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 90$ equal circles inside circle with circular hole of radius a

Figure 52: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 53: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 54: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 55: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 56: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 57: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 58: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 59: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 60: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 61: Configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

2.7 Ellipse - circle

2.7.1 $N = 18$

Figure 62: Configurations for $N = 36$ inside ellipse with ratio 2 between major and minor axis, and a circular hole with radius 0.5 centered at various parameters b

2.7.2 $N = 19$

Figure 63: Configurations for $N = 36$ inside ellipse with ratio 2 between major and minor axis, and a circular hole with radius 0.5 centered at various parameters b

2.7.3 $N = 36$

Figure 64: Configurations for $N = 36$ inside ellipse with ratio 2 between major and minor axis, and a circular hole with radius 0.5 centered at various parameters b

2.7.4 $N = 37$

Figure 65: Configurations for $N = 37$ inside ellipse with ratio 2 between major and minor axis, and a circular hole with radius 0.5 centered at various parameters b

3 Voronoi diagrams

3.1 Rectangle

3.1.1 $N = 14$

Figure 66: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 14$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 67: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 14$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.1.2 $N = 25$

Figure 68: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 25$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 69: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 25$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.1.3 $N = 36$

Figure 70: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 71: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 72: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.1.4 $N = 49$

Figure 73: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 49$
 $a = 3.05$
 $\rho = 0.788617$

$N = 49$
 $a = 3.41$
 $\rho = 0.8096764$

$N = 49$
 $a = 3.59$
 $\rho = 0.8264408$

$N = 49$
 $a = 5.5$
 $\rho = 0.7771891$

$N = 49$
 $a = 6.2$
 $\rho = 0.8317567$

Figure 74: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.1.5 $N = 60$

Figure 75: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 60$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 60$
 $a = 2.8$
 $\rho = 0.8444694$

$N = 60$
 $a = 3.75$
 $\rho = 0.7853982$

$N = 60$
 $a = 4.31$
 $\rho = 0.8447175$

$N = 60$
 $a = 6.67$
 $\rho = 0.7850059$

$N = 60$
 $a = 7.5$
 $\rho = 0.841079$

Figure 76: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 60$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.1.6 $N = 64$

Figure 77: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 78: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

Figure 79: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.1.7 $N = 120$

$N = 120$
 $a = 1.01$
 $\rho = 0.8481396$

$N = 120$
 $a = 1.19$
 $\rho = 0.8484457$

$N = 120$
 $a = 1.42$
 $\rho = 0.8567236$

$N = 120$
 $a = 1.76$
 $\rho = 0.8491482$

$N = 120$
 $a = 2.2$
 $\rho = 0.8599127$

Figure 80: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$N = 120$
 $a = 2.87$
 $\rho = 0.8537832$

$N = 120$
 $a = 3.85$
 $\rho = 0.8620499$

$N = 120$
 $a = 5.49$
 $\rho = 0.8615693$

$N = 120$
 $a = 8.48$
 $\rho = 0.8567236$

Figure 81: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

$$\begin{aligned} N &= 120 \\ a &= 14.85 \\ \rho &= 0.850821 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} N &= 120 \\ a &= 32.43 \\ \rho &= 0.8346731 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 82: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 120$ equal circles inside rectangle.

3.2 Cross

3.2.1 $N = 36$

Figure 83: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside cross.

Figure 84: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 36$ equal circles inside cross.

3.2.2 $N = 49$

Figure 85: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside cross.

Figure 86: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 49$ equal circles inside cross.

3.2.3 $N = 64$

Figure 87: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside cross.

Figure 88: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 64$ equal circles inside cross.

3.3 Ellipse

3.3.1 $N = 37$

Figure 89: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 37$ equal circles inside ellipse.

3.3.2 $N = 61$

Figure 90: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 61$ equal circles inside ellipse.

3.3.3 $N = 91$

Figure 91: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside ellipse.

Figure 92: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside ellipse.

3.4 Continuous deformation of a circle into a cardioid

For this case we use the following parametrization which has constant area of π :

$$C(u) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{2+a^2}} \cdot (\cos u - a \sin^2 u, (1+a \cos u) \sin u)$$

3.4.1 $N = 37$

Figure 93: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 37$ equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

3.4.2 $N = 61$

Figure 94: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 61$ equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

3.4.3 $N = 91$

Figure 95: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for $N = 91$ equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

3.5 Annulus with hole

Figure 96: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 97: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 98: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 99: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 100: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 101: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 102: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 103: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 104: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 105: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

Figure 106: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside circle with a circular hole of radius a .

3.6 Cardioid

Figure 107: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 108: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 109: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 110: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 111: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 112: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 113: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 114: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 115: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 116: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

Figure 117: Voronoi diagrams for some of the configurations corresponding to a local maximum of the packing fraction for N equal circles inside cardioid of area π .

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References

- [1] P. Amore, D. de la Cruz, V. Hernandez, I. Rincon and U. Zarate, "Circle packing in arbitrary domains" (2023)